

“The role and importance of interactive games in the teaching of English in secondary schools”

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Annotation: Today, the younger generation is increasingly interested in learning foreign languages. Therefore, teaching a foreign language, including English, in secondary schools requires the use of interactive methods in the classroom. This article focuses on the effectiveness of organizing lessons using interactive methods in English classes in secondary schools.

Keywords: method, interactive method, information and communication technologies, interactivity.

Аннотация: Сегодня возрастает интерес молодого поколения к изучению иностранных языков. Поэтому обучение иностранному языку, в том числе английскому, в общеобразовательных школах требует использования на уроках интерактивных методов. Данная статья посвящена эффектам организации уроков с использованием интерактивных методов в классах английского языка общеобразовательных школ.

Ключевые слова: метод, интерактивный метод, информационно-коммуникационные технологии, интерактивность.

Аннотация: Bugungi kunda yosh avlodning xorijiy tillarni o'rganishga qiziqishi ortib bormoqda. Shu bois, umumta'lim maktablarida xorijiy tilni, jumladan ingliz tilini o'qitish darslarda interfaol metodlardan foydalanishni talab etadi. Ushbu maqola umumta'lim maktablarining ingliz tili darslarida interfaol metodlardan foydalanib darslarni tashkil qilishning samaralariga bag'ishlangan.

Калит со'злар: метод, интерfaol метод, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, interfaollik.

Currently, one of the main directions in the field of improving educational methods is the introduction of interactive education and training methods. Teachers of all subjects are increasingly using interactive methods in the course of lessons. As a result of the use of interactive methods, the students' skills of independent thinking, analysis, drawing conclusions, expressing their opinion, being able to defend it based on reasons, healthy communication, discussion, debate are formed and developed. Interactive methods are many different, and all of them, like any progressive methods, first of all, require a lot of preparation from the teacher before the lesson. In the organization of these activities, the main features of the interactive lesson can be more clearly understood by considering some of its differences compared to the traditional lesson. Most importantly, all of this serves to facilitate students' mastery of subjects and increase efficiency English language classes are no exception. In particular, in the process of teaching a foreign language, language learners are under a lot of pressure and burden. For this reason many students do not learn effectively in foreign language classes. One of the most

effective ways to alleviate this situation and reduce the pressure students feel is the use of non-traditional methods in the teaching process, especially interactive games. In the process of interactive games, the main task is performed by the students themselves. In this process, the teacher acts only as a guide and controller of the process. How interesting and effective the lesson is, keeping the didactic content in line with the topic depends primarily on the teacher's pedagogical skill and creativity. Any teacher tries to use interactive methods in his lessons, using Internet resources, manuals, personal experiences of colleagues.

In our country, significant work is being done on the formation of the information society and the introduction of the most advanced information and communication technologies in all areas. In particular, the capabilities of interactive services are highly valued in this process. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the concept of "interactive" is defined as the basis for receiving or transmitting information through a computer network.

In Wikipedia, interactivity is evaluated as a concept that reveals the nature and level of interaction between objects, and it is said to be used in the fields of information theory, computer science and programming, telecommunication systems, sociology, industrial design, etc. In a word, interactivity is a system of organizing a system, and parts of this system is to achieve a specific goal by establishing an exchange of information between them. Interactive method - by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process, it serves to activate the learning of students and to develop their personal qualities. The use of interactive methods helps to increase the effectiveness of the lesson.

ILM – FAN TA'LIMDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR, MUAMMOLAR, TAKLIF VA YECHIMLAR

The main criteria of interactive education: conducting informal debates, the opportunity to freely describe and express the educational material, the number of lectures is small, but the number of seminars is large, the creation of opportunities for students to take initiative, small group, large group, class team, assignments, written work and other methods, which are of special importance in increasing the effectiveness of educational work. Currently, one of the main directions in the field of improving educational methods is the introduction of interactive education and training methods. All subject teachers are increasingly using interactive methods in the course of their lessons. As a result of the use of interactive methods, the students' skills of independent thinking, analysis, drawing conclusions, expressing their opinion, being able to defend it based on reasons, healthy communication, discussion, debate are formed and developed. In the process of interactive education, the lesson is based on the interaction of students. Interactive is derived from the English word "Interakt", that is, Inter means "mutually", "act" means action, influence, activity. Interactivity is the activity of two people, that is, the learning process takes place in the form of a mutual conversation, in the form of a dialogue (computer communication) or on the basis of teacher-student interactions. Interactivity - mutual activity, movement, affectivity, student-teacher, student-student (subject-subject) conversations occur. The main goal of interactive methods is to create the most favorable environment for the learning process by creating an environment for the active, free, creative thinking of the student, the use of his needs, interests, and internal capabilities. Such lessons are conducted in such a way that no student is left out and has the opportunity to openly express his/her opinions, what he/she has heard, read, seen. A process of exchange of ideas

takes place. Children's enthusiasm and interest in learning increases, mutual friendly relations are formed.

But in this process, special attention should be paid to individual characteristics. For example, students' age, mastery level, personal and psychological characteristics, classroom size, equipment, etc. Below we will briefly touch on some interactive games and their advantages and organizational process. "Change your seats" is a game designed to be played in a large room with a large number of students, with quality levels for upper grades, correct and incorrect verbs can be used with related participles such as present and past tenses. In elementary grades, it can be divided into parts such as letters and words that begin with that letter, objects, written names of animals or numbers, and their pictures. Let's consider this game as an example of the topic of quality levels in higher grades. First of all, the topic of quality levels should be explained in the previous lesson, and memorization of the list of quality levels should be given as homework. To start the game, students sit in a circle, facing each other. The teacher gives each participant a card with one word, that is, an adjective. There are three different levels of the same quality on three separate cards. The number of students should be 15-18 for the proper organization of the game.

One participant goes to the center of the circle. In 30 seconds, students have to show their cards to each other, look at each other's cards, find the remaining two parts of the quality on their cards and identify the owners of these cards as partners. When the time is up, the teacher says different words. Students will have to switch places with their partners when saying the word related to the quality

series. The student standing in the middle will have to find an empty chair and sit down. In this way, the process is repeated several times. Then the cards are collected, other cards are dealt and the game starts all over again. This game is useful for students' Grammar knowledge and listening comprehension skills. Because the gameplay is fun, students will easily memorize the quality levels. Based on my personal experience, 7th graders learn more than 30 adjectives after 3 lessons. those who have memorized with degrees. Depending on the didactic material, this game can be used in other subjects.

"Cooky jar" This game is also one of the most popular games. Especially in the elementary grades, it will be a very interesting process if organized with colorful handouts. This game is directly related to the song and lists the names of the pets during the song, which is especially useful for reinforcing the theme of pets. At the beginning of the lesson, each student is given cards with pictures of the same pet. As the song is being sung, each student must show the picture card of the animal that is mentioned. You can also add cards with pet names on them. After hearing it several times, the students begin to sing the song together. It follows that students develop speaking skills along with listening comprehension skills. At the same time, vocabulary increases. This game can also be adapted to other themes by changing the song. Most importantly, it is a very interesting process for students, which makes language learning easier and creates a creative mood. Another interactive game that develops students' speaking skills is the "Translator" game, in which the teacher plays the role of an alien. Students should explain to him the meaning of each item or word. In this game, students' improvisational skills are formed, and acting skills are also formed by performing various actions. It also encourages students to think outside the box. This game is mainly suitable for

upper level students, where there is a certain amount of vocabulary and the students will use them. All of the above games can be used to make the process of learning English more interesting. The most important thing is that the games and methods used in the lesson are effective and the language skills of the students are further developed.

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